

**AN ASSESSMENT ON THE READING ABILITY OF GRADE 1 LEARNERS IN
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INTERVENTION READING PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 3

Pages: 195-200

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2456

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13899500

Manuscript Accepted: 09-07-2024

An Assessment on the Reading Ability of Grade 1 Learners in Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur: Basis for Intervention Reading Program

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Abstract

This study investigates the reading behavior of Grade 1 learners in the Minabalac District, Camarines Sur, aiming to inform the development of targeted reading programs and materials. The participant demographic included 58.62% six-year-olds and 39.66% seven-year-olds, with a higher number of female learners. Parental education levels varied, with most parents having completed secondary education. Prior to the intervention, the reading profiles indicated that 56.90% of students were slow readers, with minimal numbers classified as moderate or fast readers across various categories. Following the introduction of localized reading materials designed for these learners, expert evaluations confirmed the materials were appropriate, user-friendly, and effectively facilitated learning. After a month and a half of utilizing these resources, a notable improvement in reading abilities was observed; many students progressed from slow to moderate or fast readers. The findings suggest that tailored reading interventions can significantly enhance early literacy skills among Grade 1 students, underscoring the necessity for dedicated reading programs in similar educational contexts.

Keywords: *assessment, reading, learners, intervention*

Introduction

The ability to read is one of the most significant requirements for academic success. A limited reading ability hampers a person throughout life and thus contributes to great disadvantage in vocational, family and other life goal pursuits. The goal of the basic education curriculum is to improve the reading ability of the learners; hence several public elementary schools have conducted different studies to determine the causes of low reading ability of learners.

The researcher being a public elementary school teacher, teaching grade 1 learners is concern mostly on the first reading experience of the pupil. As it is well said that "first impression is lasting" reading experience of grade 1 learners is a crucial stage in the reading process of a child. This is where his/her impression about reading will make the child better or worst reader.

The Department of Education is trying its very best to find ways in order to solve those problems. It has conducted programs and projects which could lessen the problems on reading ability among Filipino learners. The department put the low performing schools in Reading under the "Project Turning Around". This is part of the Department's task to raise the low performances of the schools specifically in Reading proficiency. The program includes teacher trainings, school administrator capability building and improvement of pupil's nutritional status as well as school physical facilities and additional instructional materials. A Whole School Approach to Master Reading and Writing was also launched. It is a model that considers the whole school as learning community where reading and writing as tools for lifelong learning. It strengthened to effect the desired changes in students' performance in terms of improved comprehension and communication skills both oral and written language. The Department also continuously delves into better ways of organizing and delivering the curriculum. (Maria Lourdes DC. Ramirez, 2012).

We know from research that reading is a language-based activity. Reading does not develop naturally, and for many children, specific decoding, word recognition, and reading comprehension skills must be taught directly and systematically. We have also learned that preschool children benefit significantly from being able read to.

The evidence suggests strongly that educators can foster reading development by providing kindergarten children with instruction that develops print concepts, familiarity with the purposes of reading and writing, age- appropriate vocabulary and language comprehension skills, and familiarity with the language structure.

Substantial evidence shows that many children in the 1st and 2nd grades and beyond will require explicit instruction to develop the necessary phoneme awareness, phonics, spelling, and reading comprehension skills. But for these children, this will not be sufficient. For youngsters having difficulties learning to read, each of these foundational skills should be taught and integrated into textual reading formats to ensure sufficient levels of fluency, automaticity, and understanding. (Lyon, G. R. 2016).

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the reading behavior of grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur thru an intervention prospect on the reading ability of Grade 1 learners in Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur that will be served as basis for development of reading program/material. It will further evaluate the learner's reading behavior after the conduct of the intervention of the program/ material name as "Basa pa More". Specifically, it seeks answer to the following problem.

1. What is the demographic profile of the grade 1 learners in term of:

- 1.1. ages;
- 1.2. sex; and
- 1.3. parent's educational attainment?
2. What is the reading behavior of grade1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur?
3. Develop a reading program to be called as "Basa pa more" as reading intervention to improve the reading behavior of grade 1 learners.
4. What is the reading performance of grade 1 learners?
 - 4.1. before the project "basa pa more"; and
 - 4.2. after the intervention of the project "basa pa more"?
5. Is there a significant difference on the grade I learners reading performance after the intervention of the project "Basa pa More"?

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive research design was use for the study. Best (in Navarro,2013) state that descriptive research describes and interprets what is. It is concerned with conditions or relations.

Descriptive research design is a scientific method which involves observing and describing the behavior of a subject without influencing it in any way. This is the most the widely-used research design as indicated by the theses, dissertations and research reports of institutions. Its common means of obtaining information include the use of the questionnaire, personal interviews with the aid of study guide or interview schedule, and observation, either participatory.

Descriptive research is a fact -finding with adequate interpretation. The descriptive method is something more and beyond just data-gathering; latter is not reflective thinking or research. The true meaning of data collected should be reported from the point of view of the objectives and the basic assumption of the project under way. Facts obtained may be accurate expressions of central tendency, or deviation, or correlation; but the report is not research unless discussion of those data is not carried up to the level of adequate interpretation. Data must be subjected to the thinking process in terms of ordered reasoning.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur, school year 2018-2019. There were two sections in grade 1; all of them were used as respondents of the study hence no sampling process was used since all of them were participants.

The reading profile of the grade one learners were assessed at the beginning of the school year. This was done by every grade 1 teachers in order to determine the reading ability of each pupil. For the purpose of this study, the prepared and validated program/material was tried out in the form of an intervention based on the assessment. The intervention was done for one grading period. After which the learners' reading ability was assessed for the 2nd time.

A total number of 58 grade 1 learners were used for this study. The ages of these participants range from 7 to 9 years with a mean age of 7.5 to 8.5.

Instrument

For the intervention material, the researcher developed a localized reading module using simple words and the use of reading applications such as Reading Bear educational video.

The reading material undergo an expert validation by 10 officials of the district of Minabalac. The researchers follow the procedure in the evaluation of the said instrument. The first draft of the instrument was presented to the advisers for corrections, comments and suggestions. In order to check the validity, the instrument was evaluated by experts. They were requested to evaluate each item of the instrument with respect to relevance, redundancy or duplication. They were also requested to give suggestions and comments for their improvement of the questionnaire.

After the validation of the expert, comments and suggestion were incorporated on the material which was subjected for a reliability test. Reliability refers to whether or not we get the same answer by using an instrument to measure something more than once. Research reliability is the degree to which research method produces stable and consistent results. A specific measure is considered to be reliable if its application on the same object of measurement number of times produces the same results.

The validated instrument was then administered to the grade 1 pupil of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study were asked from the District Supervisor and the principal of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur, to allowed the proponent to conduct the intervention program/material called as project "Basa Pa More" to grade 1 pupil. After

the granting of the permission the researchers personally conduct the intervention for one grading period.

Pre-Implementation Plan

The validated reading test enable the researchers to gather sufficient data on the reading behavior of the learners Results of these pre-survey questionnaires was checked, organized, and verified

Implementation plan

During the pre-implementation phase, the researcher gather data to identify the reading behavior and ability of the grade 1 learners and the intervention program the "Basa Pa More" was given to the learners. After a month, a reading assessment as was conducted to determine the difference in the reading ability after the intervention

Post-implementation plan

During this phase, the statement of purpose of this research was answer and the result of the study was reported and necessary recommendation was made.

On the bases of the data gathered from the reading assessment, observation and interview of teacher the project "Basa pa More" was evaluated. If found to be effective, I will further be evaluated and proposal on the use of the project be implemented in the local setting. That is to be use by all grade 1 teachers in their reading class and for remedial instruction on learners with reading difficulties.

Data Analysis

Data was tabulated and processed using the appropriate statistical tools. The statistical tool used in the analysis and interpretation of data includes the percentage, weighted mean and Spearman rank order Correlation.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered from the instrument of the study. It was presented in table form and was analyze and interpreted using appropriate statistical tools

Profile of the Grade 1 learners

Table 1. *Age Distribution of the Grade 1 of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur*

<i>Age (number of years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>	<i>Rank</i>
6	24	58.62%	1
7	23	39.66%	2
8	1	1.72%	3
Total	58	100%	

Age Distribution of the grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur is presented in table 1. As shown in the table of the 58 learners, 34 learners or 58.62%were six (6) years old; 23 learners or 39.66% were seven (7) years old and only one (1) was 8 years old.

Table 2. *Sex Distribution of the Grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
Female	37	63.79%
Male	21	36.21%
Total	58	100%

As to sex, the grade 1 learners were composed of 37 females or 63.79%and 21 male learners or 36.21 %. There are more female than male learners.

Table 3. *Educational attainment of parents of Grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur*

<i>Educational Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage %</i>
Elementary Graduate	3	5.17%
Secondary Level	7	12.07%
Secondary graduate	25	43.10%
College level	13	22.41%
College Graduate	10	17.24%
Total	58	100%

The Educational attainment of parents Of Grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur, majority of the parents were secondary graduates, with twenty- five (25) parents of 43.10%; thirteen (13) parents or 22.41% were college level; ten (10) parents or 17.24% were college graduate; seven (7) parents or 12.07 were secondary level and three (3) parents finished elementary.

Reading Performance of the Grade 1 learners Before the Intervention

Table 4. Reading Profile of Grade 1 Pupil of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur before the Intervention "Basa Pa More"

Type of Reader	Sounds of Alphabets		Syllables		Words & Simple Phrases		Simple Sentence		Sentence with comprehension		Total	
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Fast Reader (FR)	0	0	1	1.72	0	0	2	3.45	7	12.07	10	17.24
Moderate Reader	0	0	2	3.45	5	8.62	0	0	8	13.79	15	25.86
Slow Reader	8	13.79	13	13.79	1	1.72	6	10.34	5	8.62	33	56.89
Non-Reader	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	8	13.79	16	27.59	6	10.34	8	13.79	20	34.48	58	100

Table 4 presents the reading profile of grade 1 pupil of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur before the Intervention "Basa Pa More". The reading profile of the pupil were divided into five categories as: sound of alphabets, syllables, words and simple phrases, simple sentence and sentence with comprehension.

Category 1 is the sound of the alphabets or the phonological awareness, the appreciation of speech sounds without regard for their meaning, is critical to discovering the alphabetic principle the idea that letters generally represent the small speech segments called phonemes).

Category 2 is reading by syllables. A syllable is a unit of organization for a sequence of speech sounds. For example, the word water is composed of two syllables: wa and ter. A syllable is typically made up of a syllable nucleus (most often a vowel) with optional initial and final margins (typically, consonants). Syllables are often considered the phonological "building blocks" of words. They can influence the rhythm of a language.

Category 3 is reading words and simple phrases. A phrase is a small group of words that adds meaning to a sentence. A phrase is not a sentence because it is not a complete idea with a subject, verb and a predicate. The other words in the phrase do the work of changing or modifying the head.

Category 4 is reading, simple sentence. A simple sentence is one independent clause that has a subject and a verb and expresses a complete thought. Examples of Simple Sentence: 1. Joe went to the store.

Category 5 is reading simple sentence with comprehension. Reading comprehension is one of the pillars of the act of reading. When a person reads a text, he engages in a complex array of cognitive processes. He is simultaneously using his awareness and understanding of phonemes (individual sound "pieces" in language), phonics (connection between letters and sounds and the relationship between sounds, letters and words) and ability to comprehend or construct meaning from the text. This last component of the act of reading is reading comprehension.

As shown in the table, on the category of sounds of alphabets there were eight (8) learners or 13.79% who were slow readers, these pupils cannot recognize the sound of letters on the syllables reading activities; thirteen (13) learners or 13.79% were slow reader, they cannot read one syllable words, two (2) learners or 3.45% were moderate readers and only one (1) learner or 1.72% is fast reader. On words & simple phrases, one (1) pupil or 1.72% is a slow reader, five (5) learners or 8.62% were moderate readers. On the other hand, on simple sentences reading category six (6) learners or 10.34% were slow readers and two (2) learners or 3.45% were fast readers. On sentence with comprehension reading category, five (5) learners or 8.62% were slow readers, eight (8) learners or 13.79% were moderate readers and seven (7) learners or 12.07% were fast readers, they can read the sentence and is able to understand what they read.

The general reading profile of the grade 1 learners reveals that out of the 58 learners 33 learners or 56.90% were slow readers, fifteen (15) or 25.86% were moderate readers and ten (10) learners or 17.24% were fast readers. Hence there is a need of a reading material suited to the grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur.

Validation of the Developed Localize Reading Materials for Grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur

Table 5. Validation of the Develop Reading Material for "Basa pa More" Expert Validation and Try-out Using Test-retest Method

Evaluation Category	Expert Validation	
	WMean	Description
1. The reading material is appropriate for the Grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur	3.94	Very Satisfactory
2. Uses readable front size, layout and style.	3.97	Very Satisfactory
3. The material can be use by any teachers in the class at any time. (Usability)	3.98	Very Satisfactory
4. The reading material is handy	3.78	Very Satisfactory
5. The reading material goals is attainable.	3.65	Very Satisfactory

6. The reading material uses simple word that can be understood by its user.	3.25	Satisfactory
7. The reading materials is easy to use (user's friendly)	3.25	Satisfactory
8. The reading material is reliable and valid for use.	3.18	Satisfactory
9. The reading materials uses visuals to help the child understand the words	3.78	Very Satisfactory
10. The reading material makes the user aware of the sound that each letter makes.	3.78	Very Satisfactory
General weighted Mean	3.66	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 5.00 – 4.25, Excellent; 4.24 – 3.45, Very Satisfactory; 3.44 – 2.65, Satisfactory; 2.64 – 1.85, Need Improvement; 1.84 – 1.00, Unsatisfactory

The developed localize reading materials for grade 1 of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur was validated using experts. The use of reading teacher in the district was asked. They were given the materials and the questionnaire. The validated reading material was used to gathered data for determine the effect of the project called "Basa pa More"

The validation outcome is presented in Table 5. As shown in the table, the evaluators indicated they were "very satisfied" on the following: the reading material is appropriate for the Grade 1 learners of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur; the material uses readable front size, layout and style; the material can be use by any teachers in the class at any time (usability); the reading material is handy; the reading material goals is attainable; the reading material uses simple word that can be understood by its user; the reading materials uses visuals to help the child understand the words and the reading material makes the user aware of the sound that each letter makes. These statements obtained weighted mean ranging from 4.24 to 3.45 with a description of "Very Satisfactory".

The evaluator rates the following statement as satisfactory: the reading material uses simple word that can be understood by its user; the reading materials is easy to use (user's friendly); and the reading material is reliable and valid for use.

Grade 1 learners Reading Performance After the intervention "Basa Pa more"

After one month and a half of using the reading material prepared by the researcher, the learners were again evaluated on their reading ability on the five (5) categories.

Table 6. Reading Profile of Grade 1 Pupil of Minabalac District, Division of Camarines Sur After the Intervention "Basa Pa More"

	Sounds of Alphabets	Syllables		Simple Words & Simple Sentence Phrases		Sentence With comprehension		Total			
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%		
Fast Reader (FR)	All fast readers	11	18.96	5	8.63	12	20.68	136	22.41	41	70.69
		5	8.63	1	1.72	5	8.63	0	10.34	17	29.31
Moderate Reader		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Slow Reader		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0
NonReader											
Total	All readers	16	27.59	6	10.34	17	29.31	19	32.75	58	100

On the sounds of alphabets reading all of the grade 1 learners were already fast readers. There was a great improvement on the reading ability of the learners on the remaining categories as follows: eleven (11) learners or 18.96% were fast readers on syllables; five (5) learners or 8.63% were fast readers on words & simple Phrases; twelve (12) learners or 20.68% were fast reader on simple sentence; thirteen (13) learners or 22.41% were fast readers on sentences with comprehension. These comprises of 41 learners or 70.69% than have become fast readers on the five categories.

On the other hand, seventeen (17) learners or 29.31% were moderate readers, five (5) learners or 8.63% on syllables reading; one (1) pupil or 1.72% on words & simple phrases; five (5) learners or 8.63% on reading simple sentence and six (6) learners or 10.34% on reading simple sentence with comprehension.

As shown in the table there was a great improvement on the reading ability of the learners. Most of them have improve from slow reader to moderate and fast readers on the five categories used in this particular study.

Using the Mean score of the learners, it can be seen that there is a significant difference on the grade I learners reading performance after the intervention of the project "Basa pa More" using localized reading material and video material from the internet. Most of the learners have improved their reading ability and their attitude towards reading.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study the following were concluded.

There are more female than male learners.

Majority of the parents were secondary graduates,

The general reading profile of the grade 1 learners reveals that majority were slow readers.

There is a need of an intervention to enhance the reading ability of the grade 1 learners.

After the intervention using the reading materials, there was a great improvement on the reading ability of the learners, most of them have improve from slow reader to moderate and fast readers on the five categories.

Based on the findings and conclusion the following were recommended.

Create a Consistent Reading Program: A consistent, coherent, focused literacy program that emphasize phonics and decoding in early grades, focus on fluency and comprehension and develop vocabulary through planned experiences and projects.

Build Strong Team of teaches: Superior teachers: dedicated, resourceful, self-evaluative, and mutually supportive that create a culture that encourages learning, thinking, reflection, and self-analysis.

Hold Teachers Accountable: Principals hold teachers accountable for improving student achievement. The principals hold teachers accountable for learners' achievement. and use their performance data as part of the evaluation process.

Instill a Love of Learning Through Reading. Help learners learn to love reading so they will love learning and Value learning and make it fun.

Appropriately target instruction to learners who are at risk for reading failure to eliminate skill deficits

Identifies learners who need additional support and services beyond instruction and leads to assessment of reading problems before these issues become severe.

Work Together: Parents, community, teachers, students, and administrators work together for those children who need additional support, the early reading intervention is essential to providing them with the best opportunity to become good readers.

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